

Title: Ambient UX: From Factory Floors to Family Transitions — Mapping Everyday Experience in Non-Digital Systems

Preprint version – this paper has not yet been peer reviewed. A full journal submission is in development.

Author: Edward Cooper SFHEA – University of Cumbria - ORCID 0009-0004-5478-7010

Abstract:

This paper introduces the term Ambient UX to describe the user experience principles embedded in non-digital systems and everyday physical environments. Drawing on personal, professional, and familial experiences, it reframes UX not as a digital concept, but as a lived spatial and emotional reality. From factory workflows to theme park queue systems, and from school transitions to supermarket layouts, Ambient UX is revealed as both pervasive and largely unnoticed, until it fails.

The paper begins with a reflective case study from 2005, where I guided the restructuring of a major international food factory's floor layout and system design. Using video analysis, spatial mapping, and operator feedback, we reduced friction and improved workflow - unknowingly applying core UX principles years before they were widely adopted outside of digital fields. That moment becomes a touchstone for subsequent reflections: navigating poorly designed retail spaces in rural Cumbria, accessing disability-adapted ride systems at Disneyland Paris, and preparing my eldest daughter who is on the autism assessment pathway, for the complex sensory and spatial systems of secondary school.

Told, through a layered, narrative structure inspired by the work of James Rebanks, this paper blends grounded storytelling with systems-level insight. It proposes a framework for recognising and improving Ambient UX in public life, encouraging businesses, designers, planners, and educators to see the experience journeys already in place, and to take responsibility for them. Ambient UX is not a future vision. It's already here, quietly shaping our lives.

Section 1 – The Factory Was First

I didn't call it UX at the time. In 2005, I was simply working on a systems problem. I had been invited to advise the management team of an international food manufacturing company on how to restructure their production floor. The issue wasn't innovation, it was fatigue. Fatigue in the systems, in the operators, in the way the factory was simply grinding through its routines via layers of years of additions and adaptations. My role was to aid the project management team to figure out how to make things smoother, faster, less draining. What we ended up doing was user experience design. We just didn't have the words for it yet.

We began with video. Not training material, but observation. Camera angles that tracked the movement of operators from machine to pallet, across workstations and back again. Then we laid that visual data against feedback gathered from the operators themselves. Many of them had been doing these tasks for years and knew exactly where the daily friction points were:

the reach that was too far, the crate that blocked the walk space, the relay of tools that caused a delay in every third cycle. We consulted shift managers, mapped their expectations, their breakdown points, their safety concerns. We collected operational data and ran it alongside our interviews.

Together, this built a picture, but not of a factory, but of a user journey. And through ongoing reflection and iterative review, we restructured the space. The result was a more efficient, more humane system. It reduced error, saved time, reduced complexity and was eventually adopted across the company's European division. It was, in every sense, a user-centred design solution for a non-digital environment. Ambient UX, even if unnamed.

It was only years later that I began to see this for what it was. The “user” had not been a faceless consumer but the people on the ground; the ones lifting, timing, noticing, adjusting. Don Norman's original conception of design was never limited to apps or websites; he spoke of doors, buttons, and teapots long before pixels took over the conversation (Norman, 2013). We had applied the principles he described: visibility, feedback, mapping, constraints. We had listened to the users, trusted their expertise, and reworked the system accordingly. And still, for years, I thought of that work as “operations improvement”, never as experience design.

In writing this paper, I've had to return to that factory floor with new eyes. These moments are not just professional anecdotes, but part of what autoethnographic approaches describe as personal experience becoming valid empirical material (Ellis, Adams, & Bochner, 2011).

What matters here is not just the solution we reached, but what it reveals about how experience is structured into space, even without intention. That factory layout, like so many

systems in our public and private lives, was making decisions for its users whether it meant to or not. The user experience was there all along.

As this paper unfolds, I will return to that factory, sometimes unexpectedly. A moment at a supermarket till, a conversation with my daughter's new school, a family visit to a theme park. All these reveal traces of the same systemic logic. UX does not begin and end at the screen. It lives in corners, thresholds, queues, menus, corridors. It is ambient. This paper offers a way to name it, notice it, and ultimately, design it better.

Section 2 – Stacking the Bags: Micro-Moments of Friction and Flow

I'm writing this from "our" annual holiday cottage in Rosgill, Cumbria. We've been here a few days. It's quiet, green, and a little rainy. I've just come back from a short drive to the local Co-op, my third trip this week. I'll probably be going again before the end of the week. These visits, as mundane as they seem, have become strangely symbolic to me. Each one reveals something small, and something broken.

At the Co-op, the only staffed till is a small counter tucked into the corner. It once had a packing shelf, but that's gone now. In its place stands a slushie machine, brightly lit and humming, clearly a relatively new income stream. The larger, more ergonomic checkout with proper space for bagging? It sits dormant, unused. I've never seen it open in the four years we've been coming here.

For me, this small change, the removal of the shelf makes checkout hard. I have some mobility challenges. I can't stand or bend easily. Packing shopping at this counter means juggling each item as it's passed back to me over the narrow surface, then bending to the floor to drop it into a bag. It's awkward, exhausting, and for those of us with limited energy, it's exactly the kind of design flaw that accumulates and costs (Imrie, 2012). And yet I doubt many people have ever mentioned it. I never have.

This is what I mean by Ambient UX. A system that doesn't appear broken but quietly wears you down. It's not a failure in the dramatic sense. It's a neglectful design logic, where friction is tolerated because it's only noticed by those whose needs don't fit the standard mould. And because it looks tidy, efficient even the cost remains invisible.

Compare this with our experience earlier this summer, during a family trip to Disneyland Paris. This was our first proper family holiday since I received my Blue Badge. As a disabled visitor, I wasn't sure how usable the park would be. But I was surprised, and not because things were perfect, but because they were clearly designed.

Disney's Priority Access system offered consistent principles across different rides, but each adapted uniquely to the architecture, capacity, and story of the attraction. There were occasional trade-offs, such as a missed pre-show, a quieter corridor, but the experience never felt secondary. In fact, the adaptations always allowed us to stay together as a family of five, which rarely happens in hotels, taxis, or booking systems that aren't built with us in mind.

The human-centred training of staff (or “cast members”) was also evident: they anticipated, explained, adapted. Everyone knew their role, not just in operations, but in the emotional choreography of experience.

It reminded me of my own beehives back in my front garden at home. In the hive, every bee has a task. But they function not as individuals, but as a system. The hive survives through attuned interdependence. Watching cast members glide through the park, I saw the same logic: not hierarchy, but distributed, reactive design thinking. The UX was ambient and held in bodies, behaviours, spatial logic, and empathy (Norman, 2013).

The Co-op, by contrast, is like a hive that’s forgotten one of its members. Not through malice, but entropy. Design was once present - there was once a shelf. But things shifted. A slushie machine arrived. The till was moved. The bigger checkout stayed dark. And now? Packing shopping means bending over in discomfort and doing so alone.

When Inclusive Design is done well, it’s almost invisible. When it’s absent, we feel it everywhere, physically, emotionally, spatially (Clarkson et al., 2007). And the Co-op example proves that even tiny details such as the width of a counter, the location of a shelf can affect a user’s dignity and autonomy. This is what disability studies refers to as “energy cost”: the unspoken taxation of navigating systems not built for your body or pace (Imrie, 2012).

What matters most is that Ambient UX is always present, for better or worse. Disney’s system worked because it was designed for variance. It was pre-emptive, flexible, and

emotionally intelligent. The Co-op's doesn't work because it hasn't been revisited. The system has drifted. It's out of sync with many real users.

These moments, one frustrating, one affirming, both sit on a spectrum. And we move through that spectrum constantly. Ambient UX isn't an idea we can choose to adopt. It's already everywhere. The only question is whether we choose to see it, AND design for it.

Section 3 – The Castle That Wasn't Yet: Story, Flow, and the Origins of Immersion

Lowther Castle, as most people experience it today, is a curated blend of heritage, immersion, and family attraction. It has a beautifully staged museum, an award-winning play park, a thoughtful pair of cafés, a restaurant and trails that invite lingering. But in 2003, it was still mostly a dream, a half-ruin holding onto memory, not meaning. And it was in that space, in that moment of potential, that I first met James Rebanks.

James wasn't yet the public voice of farming and landscape that many now know him as. At the time, he was working as a project manager on behalf of a consultancy involved in the redevelopment of the Lowther estate. I had just graduated with a first-class degree in Media Production and had been commissioned by James and the British Film Institute to direct a short documentary as part of a national series exploring the theme of identity. James had already identified Lowther Castle as the setting. My job was to find the story and to bring it to life.

But what unfolded was not a traditional documentary. I arrived with a camera, crew and a handful of ideas, and quickly realised that this landscape required something more radical. The people we met - estate workers, gardeners, woodsmen, now elderly, all spoke with such clarity, but also with such distance. Many were remembering lives and routines long gone. So I made a decision: instead of staging interviews in neutral settings, I would let each person tell their story inside the world that had shaped them. We would project those interviews back into the physical spaces of the Lowther estate. Onto trees, onto decaying stone walls, onto the remnants of barns and staircases and re-film them as ghosts within place (Tuan, 1977).

One man, Jack, lived in the hamlet of Hackthorpe. A former woodsman on the estate and Korean War veteran, he sat in his modest kitchen, reflecting on a life shaped by war, by love, and by the land. I used a fisheye lens, a strange choice for documentary perhaps, but it allowed me to frame these participants inside their own worlds, curved and warped like memory. Jack's words were raw. He spoke of humble and harsh life in Hackthorpe and working on the Lowther estate. He also spoke of mowing down enemy soldiers with a light machine gun: "We used to slaughter the buggers," he said, before falling silent. When he resumed, he added, "Well... it was either you or them." The moment hung there — and still does. We fade to black, leaving only the tree in frame, where just beforehand Jack's stark gesture, mimicking a rake of machine gun fire flashed across its rough bark, distorted by the fisheye lens. We hear a hoot from an owl, a distant chord and the camera tracks on further into the woods onwards to the rest of the film.

I saw that tree again just yesterday with my family on our trip to the Castle grounds. I call(ed) it, Jack's tree and pointed it out to my children, who were distracted in a game of chase. The

significance of that tree, of that man and the memories of witnessing the magic of those moments was just for me.

James was taken with the process. He saw something in the projections. Not just aesthetic experimentation, but a way of thinking through space and story simultaneously. He offered help. I remember one night him turning up with a quad bike and trailer to help move our film gear across the estate. Later, he asked me to develop a series of immersive projection-based concepts for the future development of Lowther. It was still early days, but the ideas were big: storytelling arcs that would carry visitors through ruin and rebirth, spaces that would flow intuitively, designs that would prioritise emotional encounter over static information (Macdonald, 2007).

In retrospect, I was engaging with the same ideas I would later come to define as Ambient UX, but back then, I didn't have the terminology. What I had was design instinct rooted in empathy and experience: a desire to make physical space feel lived-in, meaningful, and emotionally legible. What we were building wasn't a layout, it was a journey.

That project, and those early conversations with James, taught me that heritage spaces are not passive. They are interfaces. They ask things of us: to feel, to orient, to imagine. And if designed well, they carry us through memory in a way that feels seamless, even when the subjects are complex, unresolved, or painful.

My family trip to Lowther Castle recently, some 20 plus years since that time with James and the projections, was not to remember, but so my children could play on the Lost Castle, a vast, multi-levelled play structure with slides and hidden spaces. This was designed with both child and adult in mind. There are slides and towers and sandpits, yes, but also flow lines that allow for co-navigation, rest points with visual framing, routes that encourage shared attention. A design that worked well, with accessibility where it could, but immersion when needed and a duality of user as a core design focus.

Later, as I walked back through the Lowther museum, I spotted a photograph on display in a hallway. It was of Mr Jeffery, the head gardener in the estate's former days. The same man once described to me by a 94-year-old woman we interviewed in 2003 who had worked under him as a young girl. That photograph jolted me. It made the circle feel complete.

And it reminded me, again that design doesn't begin with function. It begins with memory, with movement, with the feeling of being somewhere that understands you. This is what Ambient UX looks like in heritage space. Not touchscreen kiosks or virtual guides. But physical, emotional systems that remember their users past, present, and potential.

Section 4 – Transition Systems: My Daughter's Next UX Journey

Robyn is eleven. And this summer has marked the end of nearly everything she's known. Year 6, primary school routines, Brownies, and the safety of familiar spaces. In just a few weeks, she'll walk through the gates of a secondary school for the first time. The uniform is ready. The shoes fit. But the emotional and cognitive logistics are still catching up.

Robyn is on the autism assessment pathway. Change is hard for her, even small changes. She needs to know where things are, what happens next, how things connect, even whether the food served will be 'in date'. The new school, by contrast, is a system: timetables, bell times, complex circulation patterns, canteen codes, rules and fingerprint payment systems. These things are not inherently complex to everyone. But for Robyn, and for many like her, the transition isn't simply about moving schools. It's about navigating an entirely new user interface and one with very few onboarding instructions.

We were fortunate. The school offered additional orientation days for students who need them. They recognised that for some children, presence is not optional, it is necessary. Robyn walked the corridors early. She saw the classroom doors, the lunch queue, the locker areas. The physical layout was part of her preparation, her calming mechanism. It reduced the anxiety of the unknown, replacing it with mapped pathways. In UX terms, it was wayfinding as care (Degen & Rose, 2012).

But there's still uncertainty. I met with the school's SENCO earlier this year, and they offered thoughtful reassurances. Robyn could have a safe place to eat lunch if the canteen was overwhelming. A locker could be provided. Systems were "in place," they said. And I believe them. But systems, as I know too well, only matter if they respond at the point of use.

What's different this time is that I'm not just seeing this through Robyn's eyes. I'm also seeing it through mine, and mine have changed.

Since contracting Lyme disease and experiencing long-term impacts of Long COVID, my own anxiety levels have changed shape. I notice systems more. I anticipate failures. I try to walk through a space before I enter it, to locate the escape route, the seating, the sensory load. And over the past year, I've entered the ASD and ADHD assessment pathway myself. So, Robyn's experience doesn't just resonate, it mirrors my own in uncomfortable and clarifying ways.

Ambient UX here is not about signage or architecture alone. It's about whether a system offers emotional predictability. Whether it understands that for some users, the interface is not just about functionality, it's about a form of safety.

School, like the factory and like Disney, is a system. But unlike Disney or the factory, it rarely acknowledges itself as one. It often forgets that users vary not only in ability, but in threshold, the emotional, sensory, and energetic load they can carry before withdrawal, shutdown, or avoidance sets in (Clarkson et al., 2007). For children on the neurodivergent spectrum whether diagnosed or not, the stakes are not minor. They are relational, long-term, and deeply embodied.

Robyn worries about the lunch queue. She worries about where to sit. About where to go if she's lost. About how to know these things without asking, because asking feels too vulnerable. These worries aren't irrational. They're UX insights. She is telling me, in her own way, what the interface lacks.

As a parent, I want to clear the path for her. As a researcher, I want to hold the system accountable. As someone with shared neurodivergence, I want the world to soften, not simplify, but become attuned.

Ambient UX in education doesn't mean lowering expectations. It means increasing clarity, scaffolding, and empathy. It means recognising that orientation is not a one-off event, it's a process of becoming at ease with space and system.

We stand now at the edge of a new term. A new interface. A new map. And I hope, with every part of me that the system meets her where she is, not where it assumes she'll be.

Section 5 – The City That Forgot Itself: Carlisle as Ambient UX Case Study

Carlisle is my closest city. It's where we shop, work, meet friends and where we run errands. But despite the familiarity, or maybe because of it, the city, like many like it, increasingly feels like a case study in how public infrastructure can fail its users not through crisis, but through drift.

You begin to notice it when you try to walk with a toddler and a shopping bag. When you drive into the city centre during roadworks. When you try to find a parking meter that works or understand how to pay for it. These are not major failings. But they are daily frictions.

Accumulations of poor design that quietly shape how welcome you feel, how long you stay, and what you avoid.

The dual carriageway that cuts between the city and Carlisle Castle is perhaps the clearest symbol of this disconnection. The castle is a premier landmark, yet it sits oddly detached from the flow of daily life. Pedestrian access is possible, but not intuitive. The visual and experiential link between past and present, between heritage and high street, feels severed. There are efforts now to change this, with signage and trails, but the deeper issue is not aesthetic. It is structural. The city has not been designed as a coherent user journey, most aren't.

Ambient UX asks us to consider whether a space feels usable, legible, and emotionally navigable. In Carlisle, the signs often point in the right direction, but the systems feel out of sync. Road layouts have changed due to ongoing works. Pedestrian crossings and routes have been altered or obscured. Temporary infrastructure becomes semi-permanent, yet users are rarely updated. There is a feeling of partialness. Of systems in motion but without anchoring.

Trying to pay for parking is another small but telling example. In some areas, meters do not work. In others, signage is confusing or offers multiple, conflicting payment methods. The experience becomes a cognitive task. You're not parking, you're solving a puzzle. For residents and regular visitors, this might be manageable. For newcomers, it introduces friction before they've even stepped onto the pavement. I know first-hand, as I help at least one visitor, each time I park in the Castle Car Park.

These experiences align with what urban design theorists describe as spatial dissonance. This is a mismatch between what space asks and what the user can respond with (Degen & Rose, 2012). And in disability and inclusive design fields, such inconsistencies are not just inconveniences. They are barriers. Systems that are fragmented disproportionately impact those who already need predictability and support (Imrie, 2012).

Even something as routine as getting coffee with a friend can reflect this. In some cafés, the layout supports flow: ordering, waiting, seating, ambient noise. In others, the queue blocks access, the till is too high, the order process unclear. You are meant to adapt, but your ability to do so is assumed.

Carlisle is not a broken city. It is a place full of potential, community, and deep history. But it is a city whose Ambient UX has suffered from inertia. It has layered new decisions on top of old ones without a cohesive logic. It has added infrastructure, but not always usability. In doing so, it has subtly distanced itself from the people who move through it every day.

What is needed is not just better signage or more efficient routes. What is needed is a shift in perspective. A recognition that every urban system is already a user interface. The question is not whether UX applies, but whether it is applied with care.

Section 6 – Toward a Framework for Ambient UX

Ambient UX exists in all physical systems. It shapes the lived experience of factories, schools, city centres, retail counters, heritage spaces, and theme parks. It is not a new invention, but a long-standing layer of design that has often gone unnamed and unexamined. This section proposes Ambient UX as a standalone design term and framework, one that draws from but is distinct from inclusive design, service design, and human-centred spatial planning.

Ambient UX is concerned with what it feels like to move through a system. It is concerned with emotional, spatial, sensory, and procedural experience. It pays attention to user intuition and effort, especially where these are shaped by habits, bodies, memories, and expectations. Crucially, Ambient UX is not just about reducing friction for marginalised users. It is also about increasing clarity, engagement, productivity, and satisfaction for everyone.

Design that is attentive to user experience in physical space delivers well-established benefits. In healthcare environments, improved layout and patient-centred signage have been linked to reduced stress and increased compliance with treatment protocols (Ulrich et al., 2008). In museums, intuitive wayfinding and emotional design enhance learning outcomes and encourage longer visits (Falk & Dierking, 2000). In workplaces, human-centred layout

planning correlates with higher productivity and reduced fatigue (Vischer, 2007). In retail, the design of flow and spatial logic affects customer spend and loyalty (Bitner, 1992).

Ambient UX brings these concerns together under one banner. It highlights the importance of user experience across all physical systems, not as an ethical addition, but as a strategic core.

The following eight principles outline a framework for recognising and improving Ambient UX in practice.

1. Emotional Anchoring

Emotions shape perception and decision-making. A poorly lit hallway, a noisy entrance, or a confusing checkout all affect mood and memory. As Norman (2013) argues, affective design is not a luxury. It is central to whether users feel capable and confident. In physical spaces, emotional anchoring increases satisfaction and improves decision-making, particularly in unfamiliar or high-stakes environments such as schools, airports, or hospitals.

2. Wayfinding as Care and Efficiency

Wayfinding is not just a spatial problem. It is a performance issue. Users who can navigate confidently are more likely to engage, complete a task, or return. Clear wayfinding in healthcare has been shown to reduce staff interruptions and improve patient outcomes (Carpman & Grant, 1993). In universities and museums, it supports accessibility, but also enhances time efficiency and flow management. Ambient UX reframes wayfinding as both care and competence. It serves users and systems simultaneously.

3. Access Without Effort

Inclusion is a baseline, not a bonus. Systems that are designed to accommodate diverse needs, including those of disabled or neurodivergent users tend to benefit a wider population. Curb cuts and ramps are widely cited examples of this principle. According to Clarkson et al. (2007), inclusive design leads to fewer user errors and broader satisfaction. From a commercial perspective, better access expands market reach and reduces litigation risk. In schools, shops, and workplaces, seamless access improves trust and repeat engagement.

4. Friction Visibility and Output

Many poorly performing systems do not fail visibly. They fail through user fatigue, task abandonment, or unspoken frustration. These micro-frictions often result in lost productivity. In manufacturing environments, iterative redesign based on user feedback has led to measurable gains in output and efficiency (Vischer, 2007). In consumer environments, reduced friction is correlated with higher completion rates and repeat visits (Krug, 2014). Ambient UX makes friction visible by recognising it in everyday behaviours, bending awkwardly to pack shopping, queuing in disorganised spaces, navigating inaccessible forms.

5. Systemic Empathy and Role Clarity

Efficient systems require role clarity, shared understanding, and distributed emotional intelligence. In Disney parks, systemic empathy is taught to every cast member as part of their onboarding. This ensures that regardless of role, staff support the user journey

consistently. In contrast, fragmented systems in education or public services often result in overlapping or contradictory user experiences. Service design emphasises joined-up thinking (Stickdorn et al., 2018). Ambient UX brings this down to the granular level, where every staff action contributes to, or undermines the user's path through the system.

6. Coherence Over Convenience

Design decisions often favour short-term convenience for administrators over long-term coherence for users. Parking meters are replaced with mobile apps without testing digital literacy. Layouts prioritise display space over navigability. In many cases, what is efficient for the system becomes disruptive for the user. Coherence, the feeling that a system makes sense has been linked to increased customer trust and return behaviour (Berry et al., 2002). Ambient UX calls for design that privileges logical flow over internal expedience.

7. Designed for Memory and Retention

Emotional memory shapes loyalty, learning, and future engagement. Falk and Dierking (2000) describe how museum experiences are built not just in the moment, but in memory. Visitors who feel disoriented remember the confusion. Students who feel excluded from a classroom space may carry that forward into self-perception. In workplace design, environments that support focus and comfort improve memory retention and task persistence (Vischer, 2007). Ambient UX treats every interaction as a memory opportunity. One that either anchors or erodes.

8. Responsive Pathways (Desire Paths as Embedded Feedback)

Desire paths are informal trails created by repeated user behaviour and are the clearest visible evidence of Ambient UX. They represent real, negotiated user journeys. Disney's early park planning famously left some areas unpaved in order to observe guest movement, then paved the resulting paths (Goldhagen, 2017). These are physical critiques. They show where systems do not align with behaviour. In urban planning, desire paths can be used to inform crosswalk placement, bench locations, and green space design (Minatomirai & Lee, 2015). Ambient UX treats desire paths as data and not deviations to be corrected, but signs of human logic that should be respected.

These eight principles do not form a checklist. They form a way of seeing. Ambient UX asks us to observe what is already happening in space and to design from that understanding outward. It connects ethics with economics, empathy with productivity. It makes the case that user experience is already happening in every physical system, whether we design for it or not.

Ambient UX is not an alternative design philosophy. It is a foundational one. It calls for systems that feel humane, intuitive, and emotionally sustainable, not only because this is fairer, but because it works better.

Conclusion – Ambient UX: Seeing Systems, Feeling Design

I am writing this paper not as a theorist looking in, but as a user moving through. As a parent, a disabled adult, a designer, and a former factory consultant, I have lived through systems that worked, failed, adapted, or simply ignored the people they served. From the food production lines I helped restructure in the early 2000s, to the pathways of Disneyland Paris, the checkout till at Rosgill's Co-op, the museum at Lowther Castle, and the anxious transitions of my neurodivergent daughter — every moment contained a form of design. Every one of those systems shaped how we felt, what we could do, and whether we wanted to come back.

Ambient UX is not a new idea. It is a new name for something that has always existed in shadows and seams. It invites us to notice how design feels when it isn't digital. It brings UX principles out of the screen and into the paths we walk, the rooms we wait in, the systems we navigate, and the moments we remember.

Two decades ago, I worked on a BFI-commissioned documentary with James Rebanks, now better known for his work on traditional farming and land heritage. Back then, we explored the lives and spaces of workers on the Lowther Castle estate. I fondly remember those nights, projecting the haunting interviews back onto the walls and surfaces of the places they spoke of, barn doors, ancient trees, ruined halls, semi fallen summer-houses. We were experimenting with presence, with memory, with layered experience. Neither of us called it UX, but that is what it was. We were trying to help people see and feel a place differently, and in doing so, to preserve and reimagine it.

That experience helped shape how I now understand design. UX is not the surface. It is the system. It is the thread between memory and moment, person and space.

This paper has argued that Ambient UX is both a strategic imperative and a moral baseline. It reduces friction. It increases engagement. It supports inclusion. It improves retention. It makes systems more human and more effective. It works in factories and in theme parks, in hospitals and in schools, in cities and in checkout queues. It belongs to no one discipline and serves every sector.

If we accept Ambient UX as a legitimate field, then training, research, and professional development must follow. The principles outlined here must be embedded in architecture, planning, visitor services, education leadership, retail systems, and civic design. Cross-sector CPD in UX should be developed not just for digital teams, but for estates managers, cultural institutions, local authorities, museum designers, hospitality teams, and beyond. We need public sector buy-in, strategic funding, and apprenticeship routes that treat UX as a critical business and societal skill, not a niche digital-only specialism.

As Norman (2013) and Stickdorn et al. (2018) remind us, good design is not an aesthetic choice. It is the difference between confusion and clarity, between fatigue and flow.

This summer, I saw both sides. I saw the magic of a system designed for delight and the exhaustion of one built for convenience. I saw a city centre become a maze. I saw a child rehearse her new route to school with anxious precision. I saw desire paths worn into the ground — quiet resistance made visible. These are not just anecdotes. They are data.

Ambient UX, then, is not about perfection. It is about noticing. It is about letting users teach us where design has failed and giving them the dignity of response. It is about moving through the world with more curiosity and less assumption. And it is about naming what so many businesses, organisations, and governments have yet to see: that experience is the system.

It always was.

References – Section 1

Ellis, C., Adams, T.E. and Bochner, A.P. (2011). Autoethnography: An overview. *Forum: Qualitative Social Research*, 12(1), Art.10. <https://doi.org/10.17169/fqs-12.1.1589>

Norman, D.A. (2013). *The Design of Everyday Things (Revised and Expanded Edition)*. New York: Basic Books.

References – Section 2

Clarkson, J., Coleman, R., Hosking, I. and Waller, S. (2007). *Inclusive Design Toolkit*. Cambridge: Engineering Design Centre, University of Cambridge.

Imrie, R. (2012). Universal Design and the problem of 'special' accommodation. *Disability & Society*, 27(2), pp.235–248. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09687599.2011.644960>

Norman, D.A. (2013). *The Design of Everyday Things (Revised and Expanded Edition)*. New York: Basic Books.

References – Section 3

MacDonald, S. (2007). Interconnecting: museum visiting and exhibition design. *CoDesign*, 3(S1), pp.149–162. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15710880701311502>

Tuan, Y.-F. (1977). *Space and Place: The Perspective of Experience*. Minneapolis: University of Minnesota Press.

References – Section 4

Clarkson, J., Coleman, R., Hosking, I. and Waller, S. (2007). *Inclusive Design Toolkit*. Cambridge: Engineering Design Centre, University of Cambridge.

Degen, M. and Rose, G. (2012). The sensory experiencing of urban design: The role of walking and perceptual memory. *Urban Studies*, 49(15), pp.3271–3287.

<https://doi.org/10.1177/0042098012440463>

References – Section 5

Degen, M. and Rose, G. (2012). The sensory experiencing of urban design: The role of walking and perceptual memory. *Urban Studies*, 49(15), pp.3271–3287.

<https://doi.org/10.1177/0042098012440463>

Imrie, R. (2012). Universal Design and the problem of 'special' accommodation. *Disability & Society*, 27(2), pp.235–248. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09687599.2011.644960>

References – Section 6

Berry, L.L., Carbone, L.P. and Haeckel, S.H. (2002). Managing the total customer experience. *MIT Sloan Management Review*, 43(3), pp.85–89.

Bitner, M.J. (1992). Servicescapes: The impact of physical surroundings on customers and employees. *Journal of Marketing*, 56(2), pp.57–71. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1252042>

Carpman, J.R. and Grant, M.A. (1993). *Design That Cares: Planning Health Facilities for Patients and Visitors*. 2nd ed. Chicago: American Hospital Publishing.

Clarkson, J., Coleman, R., Hosking, I. and Waller, S. (2007). *Inclusive Design Toolkit*. Cambridge: Engineering Design Centre, University of Cambridge.

Falk, J.H. and Dierking, L.D. (2000). *Learning from Museums: Visitor Experiences and the Making of Meaning*. Walnut Creek, CA: AltaMira Press.

Goldhagen, S.W. (2017). *Welcome to Your World: How the Built Environment Shapes Our Lives*. New York: Harper.

Krug, S. (2014). *Don't Make Me Think: A Common Sense Approach to Web Usability*. 3rd ed. San Francisco: New Riders.

Minatomirai, A. and Lee, J. (2015). Experiential value and experiential satisfaction in the context of museum visitor experience. *International Journal of Tourism Sciences*, 15(1-2), pp.57–76. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15980634.2015.11434619>

Norman, D.A. (2013). *The Design of Everyday Things (Revised and Expanded Edition)*. New York: Basic Books.

Stickdorn, M., Hormess, M.E., Lawrence, A. and Schneider, J. (2018). *This is Service Design Doing: Applying Service Design Thinking in the Real World*. Sebastopol, CA: O'Reilly Media.

Ulrich, R.S., Zimring, C., Zhu, X., DuBose, J., Seo, H.B., Choi, Y.S., Quan, X. and Joseph, A. (2008). A review of the research literature on evidence-based healthcare design. *HERD: Health Environments Research & Design Journal*, 1(3), pp.61–125.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/193758670800100306>

Vischer, J.C. (2007). The effects of the physical environment on job performance: Towards a theoretical model of workspace stress. *Stress and Health*, 23(3), pp.175–184.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/smi.1134>